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Himmel un Ääd representing Rhineland

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reviewed by Jonas Faria Costa

Rhineland is a cultural landscape in the Middle and Lower Rhine region of Germany. It is mainly characterized by its shared history, language, music, customs, and cuisine, which is why its geographical boundaries are often interpreted in varying ways. Key elements that shape Rhenish identity include a variety of dialects and regiolects, such as Kölsch and Bönsch; a vibrant and distinctive local music scene; das Rheinische Grundgesetz, a collection of eleven sayings; the carnival, which is particularly popular in Bonn, Cologne, and Düsseldorf and often described as a ‘season’ in its own right; and the distinctive Rhenish cuisine.

Among the traditional dishes of the Rhineland is Himmel un Ääd, a hearty meal made primarily of potatoes and apples, accompanied by blood sausage. Its name, derived from the Rhenish dialect, translates to ‘heaven and earth’, referring to the apples growing in the trees above and the potatoes growing in the earth below. The preparation and enjoyment of Himmel un Ääd are quintessentially Rhenish traditions. Thanks to its simplicity and down-to-earth nature, the dish is a staple at local breweries, at city festivals, markets, and carnival celebrations. Its frequent presence at these gatherings makes Himmel un Ääd evoke a sense of belonging, of Heimat. It not only offers warm nourishment but also plays a vital role in everyday place-making and in shaping the identity of the Rhineland.

Among other cultural expressions, the music sung in dialect strongly reflects Rhenish identity. References are therefore often made to Himmel un Ääd as an identity-forming feature by artists such as Willy Millowitsch, Bläck Fööss, and De Räuber (Akademie für uns Kölsche Sproch, 2025b,a,d). In their song ‘Der kölsche Pass’, the Höhner even sing: ‘Am Anfang schuf dä Herr Himmel un ääd. Un dann – Bloot-

woosch. Un dann schuf hä die eetste Kölsche: Adam un Eva – Schmitz’ (Akademie für uns Kölsche Sproch (2025c); translates to ‘In the beginning, the Lord created heaven and Earth. And then – blood sausage. And then he created the first Cologne Adam and Eve – Schmitz’). By portraying Himmel un Ääd as the first of all things that God created, even before the people in Cologne and Rheinland came into existence, the tongue-in-cheek lyrics metaphorically presents Himmel un Ääd as foundational to Cologne’s identity and, by extension, also the broader Rhenish identity.

Literature

Akademie für uns Kölsche Sproch: *Kölsche Liedersammlung – Am Bickendorfer Büdche von den Bläck Föös*. 2025a. <https://www.koelsch-akademie.de/liedersammlung/song/am-bickendorfer-buedche>

Akademie für uns Kölsche Sproch: *Kölsche Liedersammlung – Dat sin vum Ferke de Schnüssjer von Willy Millowitsch*. 2025b. <https://www.koelsch-akademie.de/liedersammlung/song/dat-sin-vum-ferke-de-schnuesscher-...>

Akademie für uns Kölsche Sproch: *Kölsche Liedersammlung – Der kölsche Pass von den Höhnern*. 2025c. <https://www.koelsch-akademie.de/liedersammlung/song/der-koelsche-pass>

Akademie für uns Kölsche Sproch: *Kölsche Liedersammlung – Jeck bliev Jeck von De Räuber*. 2025d. <https://www.koelsch-akademie.de/liedersammlung/song/jeck-bliev-jeck>